

YamHub as an international platform for yam research and breeding based in Guadeloupe

ABSTRACT

Achieving global food security remains one of the greatest challenges of our time, particularly in the global south. Although much of the global focus has been on cereals, root and tuber crops have an equally crucial yet often underappreciated role. Among these, yams (*Dioscorea* spp.) stand out as a vital staple that is deeply embedded in the culture, economy and nutrition of millions of households¹. Yams feed more than 500 million people worldwide, with annual production exceeding 80 million tons, mainly in tropical and subtropical regions (<https://fao.org/faostat/en/#compare>). This crop thus contributes to food diversity, income generation and resilience in farming systems that often face climatic and economic uncertainty².

The genus *Dioscorea* includes over 600 species, but only about 7 are widely cultivated for their starchy tubers. Yet, despite their importance, the genetic improvement of yams has lagged far behind that of cereals and even other root and tuber crops, such as cassava and potato³. Indeed, yams have long growth cycles (7–9 months), erratic and genotype-dependent flowering, dioecy and high heterozygosity. In addition, working with yams is particularly labor-intensive as planting and harvesting require considerable effort, making large-scale field experiments physically demanding and costly. These combined challenges have slowed genetic improvement as compared with other staple crops, leaving farmers with only a few improved cultivars⁴.